

A Comparison of Working Methods in Industrial Design and the Creative Arts

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Abstract

The pilot study described in this paper is the first study in a programme of research concerning tools for facilitating the creative industrial design process. The specific aim was to compare the working methods of the different disciplines to identify those that might be worth investigating further in future research.

The comparison was achieved by reviewing responses from a standard questionnaire that was sent to students studying fine art, textiles, jewellery (and silversmithing), graphics, industrial design and automotive engineering. The open-ended questions focused on high level issues e.g. chosen project type, how they start projects, how and what they research, to try and gain an understanding of their working practices.

The main conclusion is that fine art students work in different ways to the other disciplines in the study. In particular, they chose to undertake projects which emphasise expressive or emotional aspects, whereas the remaining disciplines concentrated on more tangible outcomes. This indicates that fine art practitioners might be the most suitable for further investigation into methods for facilitating the creative industrial design process.

Keywords: Creative arts, industrial design, working practices, design research

Introduction

In 1999, the Tate Gallery (London), exhibited work by nine sculptors in an exhibition curated by Colin Painter (1999), called ‘At Home with Art.’ The exhibits were all products designed for use in the home environment e.g. tableware, shower curtains, coat hooks and garden tools. Each piece was mass produced and sold in *Homebase*, a UK based superstore that supplies products for home decoration and improvements. These sculptors, for a short while became industrial designers and the work produced was innovative, thought provoking, fun and emotional. Similarly, at *Alessi* (a manufacturer of consumer products, based in Italy); many innovative and emotional products are designed by individuals from other disciplines e.g. architecture. How do they do it? Do they use different methods and techniques? Does the industrial designer have anything to learn from them?

The overall aim of the research programme being undertaken is to understand the working practices of individuals in the creative arts and develop new tools and methods for use by industrial designers. There are many published methods that designers can use e.g. Jones (1992), Lawson (1997), but it is difficult to find equivalent methods for the creative art disciplines. The creative arts are a vast domain, consisting of many disciplines such as fine art, sculpture, printmaking, painting, textiles, ceramics, fashion, graphics, silversmithing, and furniture design.

The specific aim of the cross discipline study, being reported in this paper, was to compare the ways in which industrial design students work, with those of creative art students in order to identify key disciplines for further in-depth investigation.

The objectives are

- To identify the disciplines that work the most differently to industrial designers,
- To identify tools or methods previously not experienced by industrial designers,
- To collect data from a 'control' group of engineers (hard sciences) for comparison.

Method

This pilot study took place at Loughborough University. It has a Design and Technology Department offering industrial design degree courses, and Loughborough University School of Art and Design (LUSAD) offering eight degree courses in creative art disciplines. Final year students were chosen to participate in the study as they had the most experience of practicing their discipline.

Alternative methods of data collection were considered, these were:

1. Questionnaires. This enables a large sample to be targeted and is preferable if inferences are to be made about large populations of people. However, there are limited possibilities to collect in depth and detailed information (Cohen et al 2003).
2. Audio or written diaries or logbooks are another method that could reveal working practices and are likely to give rich and detailed data. However, there is the risk of participants not using them or of obtaining non-relevant information. (Sayre, 2001).

3. Discussions with members of each discipline using methods such as interviews or focus groups. These are very effective at revealing in depth detailed information but are time consuming to complete and evaluate (Cohen et al 2003).

Therefore, to be able to maximise the data obtained from this study it was decided to use a questionnaire and personal audio diaries. This would maximise the number of participants but also allow some in depth data collection. Only the questionnaire study is reported in this paper.

The questions in this study focused on the larger activities of student work such as the type of project they undertake and how they choose to research. Also, such high level questions were not affected by the phenomenon of tacit knowledge, since they were not concerned with the micro or macro level of design decision-making.

Open-ended questions were used. These enable the respondents to write their own thoughts, using their own language and terminology. This approach tends to elicit more revealing information. However, articulating answers places a greater load on the mind than closed questions, which can result in frustrating the respondent (Cohen et al 2003). To avoid such responses the number of open questions was limited to five.

The questionnaire had three classification type questions: degree course, sex and handedness. These were included for the purpose of later analysis.

The main questions were:

1. Tell me about one of your past studio or major projects.

The objective of this question was to uncover the type of project the students from different disciplines choose to undertake. This helped to determine the areas of interest in each discipline.

2. How do you like to start a project? What are the first few things you do?

This question intended to encourage the respondent to think about how they do things and particularly how do they approach and start their projects. Do different disciplines approach projects differently?

3. Do you research? If so how, and what sort of things do you search for?

How and what people research can identify the topics that are most important to them and their discipline.

The remaining two questions were unfinished sentences that the respondents completed.

These added variety to the questionnaire and maintained participant interest and engagement.

4. When working I find inspiration from...

This question aimed to identify any preferred sources of inspiration that the artists or designers may use for each project.

5. To help me generate ideas I like to...

For the purpose of this study inspiration is when ideas are formed from an external source, where as, generating ideas is considered a conscious activity. The findings from this question will help to identify preferred methods of progressing a project.

The questions were piloted with three students on the Industrial Design Masters course in the Department of Design and Technology. Two of the students had backgrounds in engineering and the third had a background in creative glass blowing, so an appropriate spread of disciplines were involved.

Questionnaires were distributed to industrial design and automotive engineering students during lectures, to ensure a good response. The LUSAD students attend formal lectures less frequently than the industrial design students, and so the questionnaires were distributed via the students' tutors and returned by the internal mail system.

Results and discussion

The questionnaire was completed by students from six different disciplines these were:

- fine art (n=23)
- multi-media textiles (n=18)
- jewellery (and silversmithing) (n=14)
- graphics (n= 8)

- industrial design (n= 92)
- automotive engineering (n=14)

The data collected from the five main questions were qualitative and to make sense of all these individual responses they were classified. Table 1 is a table of the classification terms used and which question or questions they relate to. Question three was split into three parts, do they research (part a), the type of research they undertake (part b) and the type of information they search for (part c).

Question 1	Personal meaning	When a project is strongly based on personal circumstances or past experience
	Expressive	When the purpose of the project is to portray social or cultural expression such as eco-design
	Tangible outcome	The focus of the project is strongly based on the outcome or product – Hard functionality
	Intangible outcome	The focus of the project is the emotion / experience the outcome elicits – Soft functionality
Questions 4 & 5	Question 2	
	Personal reflection	Project progression via contemplation / mind tools
	Initial project work	Project progression by physical sketching / modelling
	Expansion of knowledge	Project progression by research activities such as searching for technical, social, cultural information
	Total immersion	Claim of being inspired by everything
Question 3, Part b	Primary research	Data that was purposely obtained for the project
	Secondary research	Data that was originally obtained for other purposes
Question 3, Part c	Cultural / social information	Information that refers to wider sociological occurrences such as fashion trends / sub-cultures
	User / secondary input	Primary research activates or conversing with others
	Collecting	This refers to the respondent who actively collects artefacts or takes photographs
	Prior art	Information regarding other artists, designers, products
	Technical information	Functional data such as material specifications

Table 1, Terms used to categorise the findings.

The classification system was tested by an independent colleague, to confirm that the it was meaningful.

Student projects

It appears that fine art students do work in a different way to those in industrial design; the other disciplines appeared to be more similar to industrial design than fine art. However, this does not mean that the other disciplines were identical to industrial design, only that the differences were not so great as those of fine art. Refer to Figure 1 below.

Figure 1, Preferred type of project.

Fine art students differed from the other disciplines by choosing to undertake projects that are either of an expressive nature or where the outcome of their work is predominantly intangible. Expressive projects are those in which the aim is to represent or portray issues in society or of past movements. Intangible outcomes refer to the emotions or experience of the onlooker or artist.

In comparison, the students of the other disciplines were predominantly concerned with tangible outcomes. This is a goal for many of the disciplines, especially for industrial designers, where the production of a working prototype is one of the main academically assessed components. However, emotional design is becoming an increasingly more important aspect of new product design and needs to be a concern of design students. It is possible that these students do consider emotional design but do not base entire projects on the topic.

The textile students also require a tangible submission for their assessment but 28% of the group still manage to focus their projects on intangible aspects such as emotion. This indicates that such an emphasis is possible on courses that require specific tangible submissions.

Starting a project

When starting a project the fine art, jewellery (silversmithing) and graphic students preferred to develop their personal knowledge base to expand their empathic horizons (McDonagh-Philp and Denton 1999). The students of the remaining disciplines show no particular preference. For example, the industrial design, jewellery and automotive engineering samples were spread across the classifications suggesting that the way in which a project is approached is personal rather than discipline specific.

Student research

The majority of the sample claim to undertake research. The exception was graphic design where only 50% of the students researched if they felt the need to. The most common mode of research undertaken was secondary, with many respondents referring to the internet for information. Of all the disciplines the industrial design students appear to be the most active in undertaking primary research, however, this is still 10% of the sample. Chhibber et al (2004) found that practicing designers undertake user research to help with designing for emotion. In contrast, the fine art students who undertake expressive and emotional projects do not do any primary research. How do fine artists know when they have achieved the emotional response they were intending?

The type of data collected by the students varied from discipline to discipline. A few trends did appear such as the need for information on prior art, and with the exception of fine art, the need for technical data. The industrial design and automotive engineering students are the most keen to search for user information. However, since only 10% of the industrial design students stated that they used primary research methods it would suggest that most of the user data obtained are from either secondary sources or personal experience. This is understandable since secondary research (eg consumer reports, marketing inelegance reports) can be more effective and for the student, more time efficient. Primary research may only be considered if secondary sources do not reveal the desired information.

Multi-media textile students are unique in this study since many of them like to collect artefacts and personal photographs to use for research purposes. The industrial design students also collect items but not to the same degree.

Sources of inspiration

Figure 2, Sources of inspiration.

The students search for inspiration from different sources. Refer to figure 2. The textile, graphic and especially the industrial design students all like to review prior art. Where as, fine art, jewellery and automotive engineering students like to undertake research activities when in need for inspiration. The tangible projects that the industrial design students engage in are likely to be advancements of existing products and thus there would be many previous examples around to observe. This may not occur with fine art, thus they search for their inspiration from other sources.

Many of the students stated that they are inspired by everything and therefore were placed in the *total immersion* category. This is a genuine response, provided the student becomes immersed in their work to the degree that their subconscious is always pondering the issues of their work (Cross and Cross, 1996). Alternatively, it may have been seen as the quick and simple response to a very open question.

The automotive engineering students invest time personally reflecting on their projects, more than other disciplines. Engineers generally undertake projects by applying known principles and this reflection may assist with this process. Tovey (1986) discussed the work of four industrial design transportation students of which one of them referred to the usefulness of

this reflective time to consider current and future issues. The same also seems to apply to engineering students.

Generation of ideas

The data obtained from this question suggests that how students prefer to generate ideas is of a personal nature, rather than being influenced by formal tuition. Fine art, graphics and automotive engineering students like to progress by reflecting on their work. The fine artists also like to expand their knowledge base. The industrial design students also reflect but not to the same degree as fine art, but they do undertake more sketching and modelling.

Classification questions

This study had three main discipline areas, that of engineering, industrial design, and the creative arts. The distribution of gender in the creative arts sample consisted of 81% female. The engineering and industrial design sample were the opposite with 91% and 65% of the sample being male. This difference is not unusual since other educational institutions also record similar differences in their gender distribution between such courses (Academic office, 2002). Since the majority of students on creative art courses are female, does this mean that females are better or more willing to include emotional issues in their work? However, recruitment and promotion of these disciplines could also be the cause of such gender distributions.

The respondents were also asked to state their handedness for comparison purposes. The industrial design and creative arts sample group were in line with the national average, with approximately 10% being left handed (Tovey, 1984). However, 30% of the automotive engineering students are left-handed. This finding goes against the norm. Design and other creative disciplines tend to have more left-handed practitioners due to this hand having closer links to the right side of the brain. The right side of the brain is better at lateral and spatial thinking and is therefore suited to resolving design problems (Tovey, 1984).

Additional issues

The sample targeted for this study may not be representative of professional practitioners but the students do provide an insight into how the disciplines may differ. For this pilot study the student sample represented the most appropriate group to target.

The study also highlighted issues regarding accessing the students of creative art institutions. The distribution and collection method used relied heavily on trusting the tutors and the students to distribute, complete and return the questionnaires. The return rate was low at 27% when compared to 76% from industrial design and the automotive engineering students. The reason for this high return rate was as a consequence of accessing the students whilst they attended their lectures, thus the questionnaire was distributed, completed and collected immediately. One result of this was an imbalance of responses from each discipline. This may have affected the nature of the results.

Conclusion and future research

The main conclusions from this cross discipline study are:

- Working practices in fine art were the most different from those of industrial design,
- Fine art projects tend to be more expressive and focus on intangible aspects to a much greater degree than industrial design and the other disciplines,
- The fine art students, unlike industrial design, do not use primary (user) research data when undertaking their projects.

Students from the fine art discipline work in a different manner to those from industrial design and thus may be suitable for future research. Fine art and industrial design students are currently completing an audio diary exercise that should reveal more detailed information regarding the differences in working practices.

Other disciplines also had differences in working practice to industrial design:

- Some multi-media textile students undertake projects with intangible outcomes such as designing for emotion,
- Multi-media textile students like to collect artefacts and personal photographs for their research,
- Automotive engineering students undertake more personal reflection than the other disciplines when in need for inspiration.

The study also found that the majority of all of the students favoured secondary research methods.

Future research may concern the ways in which fine art practitioners consider and use emotion and experience in their work, and the identification of simpler and more accessible user research methods that design and art students, as well as practitioners, may prefer.

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